

DOMS OF BANARAS: A SOCIO-CULTURAL STUDY

Introduction

The modern city of Banaras has been historically known by many names, one of them being *Mahashamshan*, the great cremation ground. It has been intricately linked with the celebration of death. The Hindus believe it to be the ultimate pilgrimage (*Teerth*), where death is believed to be liberating in the religious and spiritual sense; hence they wish to spend their last days of life in Banaras, leading to their cremation on the traditional cremation sites (*Ghats*). Here the two Ghats, which are *Manikarnika* and *Harishchandra Ghats*, are the primary sites for the performance of the Hindu funeral rituals, and involvement of the family and kin of the dead and require the assistance of various ritual specialists. These specialists are the locals who follow their traditional occupations based on their castes and provide their services. The cremation rituals involve such castes as *Mahabrahmans* (funeral priests), *Nau* (barbers), and the *Doms* (funeral attendants). In my proposed study, I will try to examine the socio-culture aspects of the Doms in Banaras. The Dom community is considered one of the lowest in the social hierarchy in India, intimately involved in Hindu cremation rituals in Banaras; as such, they are also segregated from the mainstream Hindu society with the notion of impurity. The inter-community dynamics of the Dom community with the other communities of Banaras is a significant spot to define the socio-cultural status of the Dom community; sometimes, these inter-community relations reflect the status of Doms in the social hierarchy. The Doms are one essential part of the business of death in Banaras. They primarily work at the Ghats and engage in their ancestral occupation of funeral attendants. The tradition dictates that the funeral can only proceed and be successful if the pyre is lit with a fire produced by a Dom. In this proposed research, an effort will be made to study the Socio-Cultural condition of the Dom community in Banaras and its periphery, and their culture, in the background of their ecological environment, and the larger society, cultural conditions in which the community inhabits. The notion of impurity degrades the Dom community in the social hierarchy. However, they hold a crucial position in the last rituals of the dead in the Hindus.

In this proposed research study, I will discuss the behavior of these inter-community dynamics in the context of the socio-cultural study of the Dom community. Also the Psychological consciousness of particular group community is important proposition to analyze the whole intergroup dynamics; here we present the figure of intergroup relation model.

The Intergroup Relation Model

(This picture is a representational image from the Oxford Model of Intergroup relations)

On the Doms of Banaras, there is a lack of informative writing on the systematic cultural heritage of Dom community and its social status. What were the reasons responsible for the inclusion of Dom society among the untouchable castes? The geography and culture of the Hindi speaking belt have reflected the riverside funeral as a fundamental religious act, or the work of getting the last rites done has traditionally been done by the people of Dom society. In this too, the role of Dom in the death in Benaras and the funeral and funeral rites at *Manikarnika* and *Harishchandra's Ghats* has been of central and vital influence. The traditional belief is that even after death, the soul remains happy and attains heaven. Like other farmers and pastoral communities of India, there is a lack of researches on the social capital and heritage of the community, culture and its types.

Furthermore, what have been the continuities, constraints, challenges and functions of change in the socio-economic sphere of Dom society? Studying the social and cultural conditions of the Dom people's living will provide the critical perspectives and research tools to understand society. How do the Dom community's people in the Banaras region adjust

themselves to the challenges posed by it in the era of the global market that emerged from European Modernity? Dom community is one of India's poorest and most backward castes. However, their traditional occupation is being funeral attendants in the Hindu cremation sites and basketry. It is observed that they are gradually abandoning their traditional occupations as the income generated through them is not adequate to meet their basic needs. Therefore, this proposed research will also explore to what degree Dom's class mobility, education, economic conditions, political participation, alcoholism, religiosity, family, and marriage system have changed from a sociological standpoint. Studying their current socio-cultural and demographic status and the present state of occupation and employment is likely to give clues to certain new ways and means to help in their overall progress.

Ever since the evolution of the early cultural institution of society, the Dom had had its consciousness, emphasizing the importance of language, collective representation, and conception of self-reliance. There is a lot of contradiction in understanding the Socio-Cultural condition of the Dom community because this flurry of activity engaging a wide spectrum of different aspects of the Dom community, i.e., Social hierarchy, Occupation, Education, health and so forth. Most of Dom community's research is primarily based on their daily routine and its impact on their daily lives. According to the major scholarly writings of the respective fields state "their place in Brahmanical social structure shows that they were a sort of receptacle for issues of Pratiloma marriage (the female from the upper caste and the other counterpart from the lower caste) within the caste system", and strongly outlined the status of Dom community in Hindu society. See (Briggs *The Doms and Their near Relation* 1950)

Colonial anthropologists like Herbert Risley and William Crook have reflected very highly prejudiced accounts on the Dom community in their ethnographical writings. Risley, in his ethnographic details, mentioned a semblance between the Doms and Chamars. He stated that in the same way as Chamars, Doms also belonged to a low-status caste and later emphasized his study on the internal structure of the Dom community, enumerating a number of variations amid different sub-castes. Like the Magahiya Doms, which he encountered in Bihar, he states that they have complex exogamy rules, which was quite simple in the Doms of Bengal. See

(RISLEY, H.H. . The tribes and castes of Bengal: ethnographic glossary, two vols. Calcutta: Bengal Secretariat Press. The condition of Dom society and the difference between Dom caste and Dom tribe has been widely discussed in the *"The Aduria Dom of Orissa: A Monographic Study* edited by Professor *K.K. Mohanty*, this monograph also suggested strongly that the overall condition of Dom Community India is the same. The famous Ethnologist *William Crook* published his thought on Dom Community in his manuscript that the physique of Dom Community had changed due to their occupation and environment. See the tribes and castes of North-Western India. In this context, one has to take into account certain major aspects of the history of India and the city of Banaras: first, the pre-colonial, colonial and post-colonial patterns of developments; and the second, the issues of tradition and modernity. They will involve, in turn, many other issues, such as the caste system in India, religious-cultural moorings, urbanization, and the efforts to bring equality and social justice in the Dom society in the Independent and democratic India. The Indian society presents an extraordinary amalgamation of modernity and tradition, but Banaras somehow tends to hold on to its traditions. Does it hint at their value for orienting any attempt at development and modernization of the city and the region to correspond with its Geo-Cultural ethos? Overall the early works of Dom Community are focused on two main themes, one of them is occupation, and the other one is Social condition and stigmatization. These are two main themes on Dom Community where most scholars had put their energy. Nevertheless, my dissertation will try to extract the self-consciousness and Cultural determinism within the dom caste. The Dom community in Banaras is a typical case for probe in this context, likely to reveal certain social problems' complexities that demand solutions.

Literature Review

Out of the reports supplied by many ethnographers and academicians, it is worthwhile to discuss the Dom caste from the Pan Indian perspective. The Doms are prevalent not only in the Banaras district but also in other states of the country, as previous anthropological records show. When it comes to the Assam valley's population, Dalton claims that *Doms are boatmen and fishermen* (1872: 77). *"The habits of the widely spread Dom clan are as impure as those of the Ghasis* (Ghasis is one of the twenty-three groups of Scheduled Castes in Bihar), *and they get their living much in the same fashion; they are to be found in all parts of Bengal and*

Northern India, living on the outskirts of villages," Dalton continues in the context of trading classes, artisans mixed, and impure tribes. They are rarely seen labouring in the fields; that they are hired to shoot dogs and remove bodies, and occasionally as executioners, and that when they don't have any of these pleasant jobs, they create baskets (1872: 326). "Dom, a Dravidian menial caste found distributed across these Provinces, about whose origin and ethnological affinities there has been conjecture," writes Crooke (1896). Crooke goes on to say that "According to Dr Caldwell, they are the surviving members of an older, ruder, and blacker race that came before the Dravidians in India". "They are considered one of India's original tribes" by Sir H. M. Elliot.

In the words of Thurston (1909), "The Domb or Dombo caste men employed as weavers and menials in the Vishakhapatnam hill tracts. This caste seems to be descended from the Dom castes of Bengal, Bihar, and the North-Western Provinces. The Dombas, like the Doms, are despised because they eat horse flesh, rats, beef, pork, and the flesh of animals that have died naturally, and both are viewed as Chandalas or possibly by the Bengalis and Uriyas. Dombs weaves the cloth and blankets worn by the hill people, but they are also labourers, scavengers, and so on, just like the Pariah of the plains. Some of them are heavily involved in trade and, on average, have greater information than the routes who dislike them." (173- 174) (1975: 173 174). According to the 1871 Census Report, Thurston highlights the occupational status of the Doms and mentions that they are employed as housekeepers, weavers. tom-tom beaters, scavengers, petty hucksters. Quoting Mr F. Fawcett (1901), Thurston hints on their habitation and settlement and states that being outcast), they do not live in the villages inhabited by superior castes people, but away from them in hamlets (Ibid 174). The book 'Death in Banaras' centres on Hindu death rites performed in Banaras (then Banaras), India. Many pilgrims and mourners visit this sacred city from all over the region and beyond. The economy of death that surrounds these rites, as well as the ideological foundations of the same, are outlined by Parry. He continues by discussing the city's association with death and how Banaras is depicted in its religious literature. He analyses Banaras's past as a pilgrimage centre and the creation and reproduction of the rites and ceremonies conducted by priests and 'sacred professionals' for thousands of mourners and pilgrims. The book's final chapters discuss the various types of ritual experts and priests, the priestly hierarchy in the business of death, the distribution of

opportunities among ritual performers for undertaking last rituals, the method of wages, the idea of gift-giving in death rituals, and the mortuary rituals that accompany the body's disposal (cremation and immersion in the Ganges river). He further extensively discusses the idea of "bad death" and "good deaths" as well as the connection between death and sacrificial ideology. Parry's work is a powerful ethnographic tale that thoroughly examines the symbolism of death rites and the pilgrimage industry surrounding them.

The Orissa District Gazetteer - Koraput by Senapati and Sahu (1968) states, "The name Domb or Domba is said to be derived from the word Dumba meaning devil, in reference to the thieving propensities of the tribe, The Dombs are a Dravidian caste of weavers and menials found in the hill tracts of Vishakhapatnam. This caste appears to have spread over Bengal, Bihar, and Madhya Pradesh are extensively or engaged in trade and have more knowledge of the world than the Ryot who despise them. In the census report of 1871, it was noted that the Dombs carried on the occupation of weaving in many villages. However, in and around Jeypore, they are employed as housekeepers, tom-tom beaters, scavengers, and other menial duties. Those people are called Paidi by Telugu, Domba by Savaras and Pana by Khonds. They are the weavers, traders, moneylenders of the hill tribes, being very useful as middlemen between the Khonds, Gadabas and other hill people on the one hand and the traders of the plains on the other. They have been recognized as Scheduled Caste" (1966: 92).

The Orissa District Gazetteer - Koraput by Sahu and Senapati (1968) states, "The Dombs are a Dravidian caste of weavers and menials located in the hill regions of Vishakhapatnam. The terminology Domb or Domba is claimed to be derived from the word Dumba, which denotes devil, in reference to the tribe's thieving tendencies. This sub caste appears to have expanded over Bengal, Madhya Pradesh and Bihar. They are heavily involved in trade and have a greater understanding of the world than the Ryot, who detest them. In the 1871 census, it was observed that while the Dombs continue to weave in many villages, they are employed as scavengers, housekeepers, tom-tom beater and other menial jobs in and around Jeypore. Telugu calls them Paidi, Savaras call them Domba, and Khonds name them Pana. They are hill tribal weavers, dealers, and moneylenders who serve as a vital link between the Khonds, Gadabas, and other hill people on the one hand and the plains traders on the other. They are categorized as a Scheduled Caste." (1966). Orissa District Gazetteer-Koraput (Revised Report, 1966), Chapter-

III: People. PP. 93-97. According to the Shalini Randeria, Carrion and corpse: Conflict in categorizing untouchability in Gujarat, she discusses in her paper that how the higher castes prevent the entry of marginalized people into the higher social milieu. Such as Dom, Nai, Chamar, Dhobi . She also declassified a wide range of classifications amongst the Dom community

Research Gap

Since I opted for this research topic for my dissertation, I have found some key eccentricity of the Dom community. I discovered that culture had a considerably bigger influence on humans than the surrounding environment. Particular groups possess the ability to adapt to any environment was due to their culture. As a result, The Dom has Cultural Determinism in their milieu.¹ Different societies and castes see themselves as superior and labeled certain people as "savages" while others are labeled "civilize" or cultured. So most research on this field is devoid of the understanding of group dynamics; that is how Dom community portrays themselves to other communities and the nature of intergroup relation of Dom Community.

Objectives of the Proposed Study

1. To identify the nature of inter-group relation of Dom community.
2. To identify the causation of segregation sentiments in the Dom Community of Banaras.

Research Hypotheses

1. The Dom Community is socially alienated in urban landscape of Banaras.

¹See, The. oxford Reference book for Cultural Determinism.

2. The role of Collective consciousness is an important catalyst for the evolution of Dom Community as a separate proud Cultural group in Banaras.
3. The proponents and thinkers of Indian politics and global capitalism promoted the structural exploitation of the Dom Community of Banaras in a new form with a psychological explanation of the sense of pseudo-superiority.

Proposed Methodology for the Research Work

The intergroup relations of any Community are simply a matter of directly addressing the norms, notions and most often, prejudice. In this proposed dissertation, I will try to show that this is not the case. Instead, through my research, I will try to demonstrate how implicit theories contribute to prejudice and destabilize intergroup relationships, even when the individuals are not prejudiced. To know this Group–Dynamics, We will frame a questionnaire for the Dom community and the surrounding other groups. The purpose of this study will be to review the ethnographic details of Doms. For this purpose, I will attempt by drawing the Structural Profile and Cultural Profile of Doms. Before studying any caste or tribe, it is essential to draw a brief history or trace the origins of the subject community. My study method will be based on rapport formation with the Doms and in-depth, focused interviews. The interview will be unstructured, knowing the practical limitations of the study like language, comprehension, and minimum level of education is some of them. The secondary sources like government data and the archival materials based on the ethno history of Doms will also back the entire study. Taking this into account, the nature of this research will be exploratory.

Relevance of the proposed study for society

As the established norm of any sociological/ethnographical studies depicts the light on social background and the living conditions of the social groups, but our study does provide not only data based on sociological or ethnographical standpoint but also covers the discourse and its relation with other groups and communities in their proximity. It has become gradually essential to examine how experiences of the Dom community in their centuries-old

occupational environment, due to which they are also called as the custodians of the salvation, have been shaped by not only the more significant economic and socio-cultural factors by the change in the material conditions but also by the developments accomplished by the state which has a direct link in influencing their living conditions. This research aims to present a response to that question through the analysis of experiences and socio-cultural conditions of Dom community in the Banaras district region. The emphasis will be laid on to the socio-cultural aspects of norms and traditions of the Dom community which is also an important element to understand the true nature of intergroup relations of the Doms as a single community. The proposed research will try to understand and analyze what are the ways in which the members of the Dom community respond to challenges they face in their day to day life while holding the lowest rank in the social hierarchy, the institutions they decide on to approach for aid and the reasons that governs the choices made by them. This investigation and analysis will be done by putting the voices of the Dom community and their narratives at the center of analysis. Also this proposed research study sheds new light on the processes that drive intergroup relations and suggests a novel path to improving intergroup relations—changing implicit theories.

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